

Puerto Rico's Human Development Index and Inequality-Adjusted Human Development Index (2013 – 2022)

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Research Note

Abstract

This research note analyzes Puerto Rico's socioeconomic development from 2013 to 2022 through the lens of the Human Development Index (HDI) and its Inequality-Adjusted counterpart (IHDI). Developed by the United Nations Development Programme (UNDP), these indicators provide a multidimensional framework for understanding development, encompassing health, education, and income. Unlike GDP, which focuses solely on economic output, the HDI captures broader aspects of human development, while the IHDI highlights inequalities within these dimensions. Puerto Rico's recent trajectory reveals progress from medium to high development levels, driven largely by federal recovery funds. However, significant income inequality persists, as shown by the gap between the HDI (0.868) and IHDI (0.700).

JEL Classification: O15, I31, R11

Keywords: Human Development Index, Inequality, Puerto Rico

Resumen

Esta nota de investigación analiza el desarrollo socioeconómico de Puerto Rico entre 2013 y 2022 a través del Índice de Desarrollo Humano (IDH) y su contraparte ajustado por desigualdad (IDHD). Desarrollados por el Programa de las Naciones Unidas para el Desarrollo (PNUD), estos indicadores proporcionan un marco multidimensional para comprender el desarrollo, abarcando salud, educación e ingresos. A diferencia del PIB, que se centra exclusivamente en el rendimiento económico, el IDH captura aspectos más amplios del desarrollo humano, mientras que el IDHD destaca las desigualdades en estas dimensiones. La trayectoria reciente de Puerto Rico muestra avances de niveles de desarrollo medio a alto, impulsados principalmente por los fondos federales de recuperación. Sin embargo, persiste una desigualdad significativa en los ingresos, como lo demuestra la brecha entre el IDH (0.868) y el IDHD (0.700).

Clasificación JEL: O15, I31, R11

Palabras clave: Índice de Desarrollo Humano, Desigualdad, Puerto Rico

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1. Introduction

When evaluating the performance or development of an economy, the choice of socioeconomic indicators to be used is of utmost importance. The indicators we study shape our understanding of progress and therefore also affect the formulation of future economic policies. Gross Domestic Product (GDP) and Gross National Product (GNP) have historically been the indicators used to measure Puerto Rico's economic trajectory. Like any indicator, they have strengths and limitations in their ability to capture the level of socioeconomic well-being of the population. These indicators measure the value of the production that takes place in Puerto Rico, but do not consider critical aspects such as health, education or equity in opportunities for people to improve their standard of living. In other words, indicators such as GDP measure economic growth; but they do not measure development.

These limitations are not unique to Puerto Rico. To address them, the United Nations Development Programme (UNDP) designed the Human Development Index (HDI), which is based on three key dimensions of development: living standards, health, and education. The HDI offers a more comprehensive view of socioeconomic development, emphasizing the importance of addressing not only production but also people's well-being. However, the HDI does not account for inequalities in the distribution of development outcomes. For example, an economy with a high HDI may mask significant disparities, where a privileged minority enjoys very high levels of development, while the majority live in deprivation. This is critical because economic growth often disproportionately helps certain groups while leaving others behind. The Inequality-Adjusted Human Development Index (IHDI) addresses these issues by adjusting the HDI based on observed inequalities in income, education, and life expectancy. By incorporating inequality into its analysis, the IHDI reflects the extent to which development benefits are equitably distributed among the population.

When first introducing the inequality-adjustment, the UNDP (2010) argued the HDI can be considered as a measure of potential development, while the IHDI as a measure of actual development. In an economy with elevated levels of inequality, such as Puerto Rico's, this distinction is particularly important. While the HDI offers valuable information on the *potential* levels of development in Puerto Rico, the IHDI measures the actual level of socioeconomic development. The sub-indices of the IHDI capture disparities in health, living standards, and education across the population, offering insights into the extent to which socioeconomic development is equitably experienced by most residents. As will be discussed below, the gap between the HDI and the IHDI in Puerto Rico can offer valuable insights into the distribution of opportunities and challenges facing Puerto Rican society. This, in turn, can guide policy-making that addresses inequalities and fosters inclusive and sustainable development.

UNDP publishes these indicators for most countries in the world in an annual report. Unfortunately, Puerto Rico is not included in that report. In 2016, the Institute of Statistics estimated and published these indicators with 2012 data. However, since then the exercise has not been repeated. As part of a collaboration agreement between the University of Puerto Rico-Mayagüez Campus (UPRM) and the Economic and Social Planning Program (PPES by its Spanish acronym) of the Puerto Rico Planning Board, these indicators were estimated and published in the agency's 2024 Economic Report to the Governor of Puerto Rico. The method and findings are summarized in this research note.

2. Method and Results

The UNDP methodology was adopted to estimate the HDI and IHDI (UNDP, 2022). UNDP (2022) uses *life expectancy at birth* data to estimate the health index; *Gross National Income per capita (PPP 2017)* for the income index; and *expected years of schooling* and *mean years of schooling* for the education index. For each, UNDP (2022) sets predetermined maximum and minimum values to transform these indicators into indices with values between zero (0) and one (1). The HDI is then estimated as the geometric mean of the three sub-indices. Once the HDI is obtained, an Atkinson inequality coefficient is estimated for each subindex. With these, the HDI is adjusted and the IHDI is finally produced.

For adjustment for inequality in the dimensions of income and education, UNDP (2022) typically uses microdata from each country. In the case of health, an initial exercise is carried out with Life Tables, where life expectancy data for each age in a hypothetical cohort of 100,000 people is used, and with this the Atkinson coefficient is estimated. In the case of Puerto Rico, the inequality adjustment for the income index was carried out using household income obtained from the Census Bureau's Puerto Rico Community Survey Public-Use Microdata Samples. The biggest limitation of this data is that it is self-reported income. Although the survey is mandatory, the imposition of penalties for inaccurate or non-completion of the form has historically been unusual. In the case of health, life expectancy at birth for 2022 has not been published. Therefore, the latest available year (2021) was used. Although Life Tables can be generated for age groups in Puerto Rico, the data required to generate Life Tables with the life expectancy of each specific age are not published. Therefore, it was not possible to estimate the Atkinson coefficient of this indicator following the UNDP methodology, which recently underwent a significant methodological review in this dimension. Instead, the Atkinson Coefficient of health estimated by the Institute of Statistics (2016) for 2012 was used, which was estimated using the UNDP methodology at the time, and is therefore comparable with the values of other jurisdictions. In the case of expected years of schooling, mean years of schooling, and the Atkinson coefficient of mean years of schooling, they were also estimated using microdata from the Census Bureau's Puerto Rico Community Survey.

Table 1 shows the socioeconomic indicators that were used to estimate the indices: life expectancy³, Gross Product per capita (constant prices 2017),⁴ mean years of ⁵schooling, and expected years of schooling⁶.

³ Source: World Bank

⁴ For the purposes of this exercise, the Gross National Product per capita estimated by the Puerto Rico Planning Board is acceptable as a substitute for the Gross National Income Per Capita.

⁵ Estimated with microdata from the Puerto Rico Community Survey.

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Table 1. Socio-economic indicators

Year	Life Expectancy	Gross Product per capita (Constant Prices 2017)	Mean years of schooling	Expected years schooling
2013	78.78	\$20,595	11.48	16.32
2014	78.93	\$20,512	11.59	16.34
2015	79.69	\$20,693	11.71	16.35
2016	80.27	\$20,741	11.79	16.43
2017	79.26	\$20,514	11.88	16.47
2018	79.77	\$20,287	11.93	16.51
2019	79.06	\$21,140	12.02	16.55
2020	78.04	\$20,210	12.11	16.61
2021	80.16	\$20,277	12.23	16.61
2022	*	\$21,254	12.35	16.56

Table 2 shows the three sub-indices and the HDI, without adjustment for inequality. As mentioned above, these indices reflect *potential* levels of development. Table 3 shows the three sub-indices and the IHDI, which reflect the current levels of socioeconomic development in Puerto Rico.

Table 2: Human Development Indices
Puerto Rico
2013-2022

Year	Health Index	Income Index	Education Index	Human Development Index
2013	0.904	0.805	0.840	0.849
2014	0.907	0.804	0.844	0.851
2015	0.918	0.806	0.849	0.857
2016	0.927	0.806	0.853	0.861
2017	0.912	0.804	0.857	0.856
2018	0.920	0.802	0.860	0.859
2019	0.909	0.809	0.865	0.860
2020	0.893	0.802	0.869	0.854
2021	0.926	0.802	0.872	0.865
2022	0.926*	0.810	0.874	0.868

**Table 3: Inequality-Adjusted Human Development Indices
Puerto Rico
2013-2022**

Year	Health Index Adjusted for Inequality	Inequality- Adjusted Income Index	Education Index Adjusted for Inequality	Human Development Index Adjusted for Inequality
2013	0.832	0.501	0.751	0.679
2014	0.834	0.500	0.759	0.681
2015	0.845	0.498	0.765	0.685
2016	0.853	0.497	0.770	0.689
2017	0.839	0.492	0.774	0.684
2018	0.846	0.493	0.780	0.688
2019	0.836	0.495	0.785	0.688
2020	0.822	0.494	0.792	0.685
2021	0.852	0.494	0.798	0.695
2022	0.852	0.501	0.804	0.700

Analysis

As mentioned above, the HDI (Table 2) reflects levels of potential development, while the IHDI (Table 3) reflects current levels of development. A significant gap can be observed between the HDI (0.868) and the IHDI (0.700). This is in line with other indicators of inequality in Puerto Rico, such as the GINI Coefficient estimated by the Census Bureau, and with the findings of the Institute of Statistics for the year 2012. Since the IHDI reflects socioeconomic reality, we will focus on these adjusted indicators in the analysis below.

Figure 1 shows that the IHDI increased between 2013-2016. It then remained relatively stable between 2016 and 2020, although with reductions in years with significant events, such as Hurricane Maria and the COVID-19 pandemic. During that period, between 2013 and 2020, Puerto Rico remained at levels of socioeconomic development considered "medium development" by the UNDP. The last two years studied, 2021 and 2022, represented a change in that trend, with consecutive increases that raised Puerto Rico to the threshold from which UNDP classifies economies at a high level of socioeconomic development. The finding coincides with what is observed in other macroeconomic variables given the impact of federal recovery funds.

Figures 2 to 5 provide context through data from selected countries through UNDP's development level categories, obtained from the most recent UNDP report (Report 2021-2022). This allows us to observe how Puerto Rico compares with the rest of the world in the dimensions of human development.

Figure 2. Inequality-Adjusted Education Index 2021-2022

Figura 3. Inequality-Adjusted Income Index 2021-2022

Figure 4. Inequality-Adjusted Health Index 2021-2022

Figure 5. Inequality-Adjusted Human Development Index 2021-2022

3. Conclusion and Policy Implications

In 2022, the residents of Puerto Rico achieved an improvement in their wellbeing, reaching the UNDP's threshold of high human development. According to the analysis of the sub-indices adjusted for inequality, this was largely because Puerto Rico compares favorably with the rest of the world in life expectancy and schooling. As seen in Table 3, living standards, as measured by the income-adjusted index for inequality, are at their highest level since 2013. However, in this dimension Puerto Rico still lags behind many economies, largely due to the elevated levels of inequality that persist. In fact, the significant gap between the HDI (0.868) and the HDI (0.700) suggests that, if Puerto Rico were to reduce its levels of inequality, it could reach the levels of socioeconomic development currently enjoyed by economies such as the United States, Canada, or Japan, among others.

The economic stimulus of reconstruction funds has surely been a key factor in the progress seen in recent years. However, this analysis of human development indices suggests that, with a focus on poverty and inequality reduction, and economic policies aimed at identifying and eliminating structural socioeconomic barriers to employment and social mobility, Puerto Rico could sustain its progress and potentially achieve development levels comparable to high-income economies. Addressing these structural issues would not only mitigate the risks of regressing to lower levels of socioeconomic development after the disbursement of recovery funds but also lay the foundation for long-term sustainable development.

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